

Review of the Literature: A Global Perspective on the Impact of Leadership Styles on Organizational Performance

Author Details: Bogosi Monyamane (Doctorate Student)

M.Ed Educational Leadership; EMSc in Finance; MSc in Computer Systems Management; BSc in Computing; Certificate in Business Studies and Information Technology; Certificate in Education: Department of Student Affairs – New Era College of Arts, Science and Technology, Botswana.

Abstract

For the reason that it is widely presumed that the effectiveness of a leader has a significant impact on organizational performance, this, has led to heightened research focused on the relationship between leadership and organizational performance. Similarly, the purpose of this study was to investigate the theoretical aspects of this concept, evaluate various leadership styles, and examine evidence regarding the efficacy of leadership styles in optimizing organizational performance. Qualitative Content Analysis was used to analyze relevant journal articles, government publications and books in order to achieve three main goals: (1) exploring the concept of organizational performance in relation to leadership; (2) identifying methods for measuring organizational performance at its core; and (3) evaluating the effects of different leadership styles on organizational performance. The results indicate that the charismatic leadership style is the most effective when compared to other approaches in that it can increase employee morale and productivity, thereby improving overall organizational performance. Correspondingly, the transformational and democratic leadership styles are found to improve organizational performance. Furthermore, it is established that the situational leadership style is effective when it employs either the charismatic, transactional, and or transformational leadership approach. Therefore, this study recommends that leaders ought to: (1) utilise feedback from subordinates to assess their leadership impact; (2) reflect on their leadership journey; (3) use leadership assessment tools to identify their strengths and weaknesses for growth opportunities; and (4) employ leadership styles that maximize employee engagement and productivity preferably the charismatic leadership style.

Keywords: Leadership; Leadership Styles; Leadership Assessment; Organizational Performance

Introduction

A person who possesses the ability to lead is a great asset to any organization, group, or department. Research has revealed that effective leaders possess a specific personality profile. In essence, people who emerge as natural leaders set clear guidelines for behavior, reward good performance, provide feedback, and take a management role in assigning tasks to others. They also possess, among other things, high emotional stability, good motivational and mentoring skills, a strong vision for success, and can share this vision in a way that inspires others. Unfortunately, those whose personalities differ greatly from this ideal will likely feel unnatural leading others, and may end up struggling should they find themselves in such a position. To be an effective leader takes hard work. Those who have the desire and the determination to sharpen their wits, hone their skills, and accentuate their virtues can pull away and deftly lead others to success.

Boyatzis, Goleman and McKee (2002) have revolutionized how we view leadership; their findings posit a new dimension of endeavor, for leaders: ‘emotional intelligence (EI)’ which makes the critical difference between a successful and unsuccessful leader. Boyatzis et al. (2002) see a well-deployed EI capability making a demonstrable impact in all realms of endeavor for both leaders and managers, regardless of the gender or role of those being led. Boyatzis et al. (2002) disagreed with the idea that leadership was about power or having supervisory ability, instead claiming that it was about helping people achieve a goal. Boyatzis et al. (2002) believed in democratic management, giving employees chances to develop and grow without disregarding order. Their observations on how to inspire and involve employees in an organization's mission are still relevant today, showing amazing foresight on the link between leadership and organizational success.

Other researchers, Muijs (2011) asserts that leaders set values, culture, change tolerance, and employee motivation; they create strategies and handle their implementation and effectiveness. Leaders are found at every level in any institution or organization (Rachin, 2001); thus, knowing about the styles of leadership in a way helps understand the traits the leader possesses. Mullins (2002) emphasized that one can approach and know the leader better based on these traits. A leader could understand his/her own leadership style. Either he/she can follow the pattern attached to the particular style or deviate from it and follow another pattern.

Given how leadership can influence organizational performance, it's worthwhile to examine the various types of leaders and how they might influence the performance of the organizations they lead. This study was carried out against this backdrop.

Background

Messick and Kramer (2004) teach us that leadership theories typically describe leaders according to their traits or how they use power and influence for achievement. From a trait perspective, these leaders may be classified as autocratic, democratic, bureaucratic, or charismatic (Adebakin and Gbadamusi, 1996). On the other hand, when approaching leadership from the perspective of exchanging power to gain results, traits or how they use power and influence for achievement. From a trait perspective, these leaders may be classified as autocratic, democratic, bureaucratic, or charismatic (Adebakin and Gbadamusi, 1996). On the other hand, when approaching leadership from the perspective of exchanging power to gain results, the types of leader are situational, transactional, or transformational (Qiu, 2008). Being aware of different leadership roles can encourage meaningful dialog for desired outcomes, and it is important to remember that all leaders are not equal, and vary in quality within industries or organizations alike (Stogdill, 1948). According to Stogdill (1948), distinguishing an individual leader's style is essential in gauging quality and effectiveness in relation to organizational performance.

Problem statement

The field of leadership is pluralistic, with a variety of opposing viewpoints and an unavoidable lack of consensus regarding the precise parameters of the discipline (Ejiofor, 1989). One major topic of discussion has been whether leadership is a separate discipline or merely a subset of the larger field of management research. It is stated that successful leaders do many things that contribute to their success, but it can be difficult to identify all of the components that contribute to their success. Generally, they give workers recognition for their work, ensuring that their efforts meet the collective goals of the organization (Mullins, 2002). The most traditional form of motivation is offering monetary rewards or diminishing fears, which are effective up to a certain point (Bhargavi and Yaseen, 2016). People are not machines, though, and if their needs for love, respect, and accomplishment are ignored, then performance and morale suffer.

As difficult as it is for leaders to understand their followers entirely, it can be just as difficult for followers to recognize the leader for who they truly are (Bhargavi et al., 2016). Perceptions get clouded by expectations from past experiences and preconceived notions. Contrariwise, poor leadership often arises from misunderstandings between leaders and their subordinates, and this leadership gap is suffered by many organizations across the globe, as evidenced by many researchers, such as Suri (2016), Tandoh (2011), and Amos, Ristow, and Staude (1999) in Africa; Iqbal, Anwar, and Haider (2015); and Elenkov (2002) in Asia; Judge and Piccolo (2004) in America; and Gavrea, Ilies and Stegorean (2011) in Europe. These are some of the few research findings that underpin the challenges faced by leadership across the globe.

Research objectives

This study was driven by the three objectives as follows:

- Explore the concept of organizational performance in connection to leadership
- Identify methods for measuring organizational performance at its core
- Evaluate the effect of different leadership styles on organizational performance

Significance of the study

The process of determining and achieving the organization's goals is central to leadership and management. Thus, these findings may provide a point of reference for aspiring leaders and managers, as well as current leaders and managers working in various fields or professions, in terms of which leadership style to employ in order to optimize human capital and organizational performance driven by external and internal environments.

Literature review

The literature review focuses on the concept of organizational performance and how different levels of organizational performance are evaluated. Leadership philosophies are also discussed in depth because they have an impact on organizational performance.

The concept of Organizational performance

Let's separate these two words: "Organizational" which is derived from "organization," and an organization is a group of people who are organized and who come together to work towards a common goal. According to Noyé (2002), "performance" refers to the action of carrying out a particular task or set of tasks, and it is evaluated based on how successfully an individual or structured group carries them out. The analysis of an organization's performance in relation to its objectives and goals is thus referred to as "organizational performance." Another option is to contrast the intended and actual results. Success in business is one thing, but effectiveness is another. It is impossible to come up with a single, agreed-upon definition of performance, according to Annick Bourguignon, because it is so closely related to the goals. Thus, achieving a certain level of performance is necessary for any objective or purpose to be fulfilled.

According to author Michel Lebas (1995), "organizational effectiveness" is a concept used to gauge how effectively a company achieves its goals with the aid of available resources without placing an undue burden on its workers. It concerns the company's ability to produce the desired quantity of goods and/or services, the effectiveness of its operations, and the amount of waste generated. According to a study by Whooley (1996), setting up an effective workplace can be difficult because success criteria differ from organization to organization depending on goals and current market conditions. A company is said to be performing well when it achieves its goals and maximizes its output.

In today's business environment, effective organizational performance is when a business can achieve its goals in an ever-shifting environment. It is critical to remember that organizational performance is subjective; at first glance, one might believe that performance is directly related to financial results, as Lebas (1995) asserted. Researcher Lebas (1995) indicates that achieving successful organizational performance relies on a variety of factors, which should all be reflective of the company's core values. These could include shareholder value, social systems, market share, or organizational culture. Historically, it was only judged on the output of results and financial returns. Generally speaking, organizational performance can be divided into three categories, which include: (1) financial performance; (2) market performance; and (3) shareholder value.

Since organizational performance evaluation is largely subjective, as indicated by Lebas (1995), it is therefore important to keep in mind that the three main aspects of improvement should be prioritized so as to manage organizational performance effectively. Folan (2007) defined these aspects as follows:

- **Financial Performance:** "When it comes to financial performance, we're talking about a company's policies and operations in terms of monetary value." Measuring return on assets and return on investment is a good way to gauge performance, but you can also assess it by looking at "value added."

- **Product Market Performance:** "We measure market performance to determine how well a product or service is doing in the market. This focuses on things like a product's increase in market share or whether an upgrade caused an uptick in sales. When referring to a single product rather than an entire organization, it's referred to as "product-market performance."
- **Shareholder Value:** People often regard the extent to which a company improves its shareholders' wealth as the ultimate barometer for success. This concept is also known as "shareholder value," which can be determined by a company's market capitalization.

Many researchers have observed that organizations differ greatly because of a variety of factors that make each unique (Bass and Avolio, 1994); these factors include their objectives and strategies used to achieve goals. All these elements can be grouped into:

- **External factors:** These factors are those surrounding the organization and are not under its control, but still affect its development, performance, and structure. They include: Economic factors; Socio-economic factors; and Political-administrative factors.
- **Internal factors:** These are those factors within the organization, characteristics such as: Purpose; Mission; Values, Culture etc.
- **Individual choice factors:** Teams or individual decisions about expected costs and/or benefits.

The environment within which the business operates is integral to a company's success or failure, and leaders should always strive to create a unified relationship between their organization and both the internal and external environment (Bass et al., 1994). Bass et al. (1994) further highlights that internally, this includes elements such as the employees and their collective organizational culture, values, and norms; these elements may have an impact on the entire business or just certain managers or personnel. Similarly, it's clear that a manager's leadership style can have a profound impact on how employees behave in the workplace.

Researcher Reynaud (2003) compares older and modern managers, arguing that older and more traditional managers may favor giving orders and measuring strictly their results, while contemporary managers empower and engage their team to make decisions, enabling them to shape their own work style while measuring not only outcomes but employees' emotional wellbeing. Ultimately, it is managers who wield the power to change their leadership style. Reynaud (2003) postulate that organizations have two layers that make up their external environment: the general and task environments. The general environment is made up of more abstract, longer-term elements that influence an organization's activities, including economical, technological, sociocultural, political-legal, and international factors. On the other hand, the task environment affects the organization more immediately through competitors, customers, suppliers, regulators, and strategic partners.

Measuring Levels of Organizational Performance

When it comes to organizational performance, organizations are always looking for ways to improve, thus measuring performance is so significant, just as it is when assessing any other type of performance. Managers and leaders can assess performance at all levels of the organization and identify areas for improvement (Reynaud, 2003), some of the common approaches to measure performance include the following:

i. Individual Performance

Individual Performance focuses on aspects of work that are best achieved by individuals working on their own, which performance has deeper levels which include the following:

- **Task Performance:** these points out the completion of the assigned tasks to an individual; the quality of their work, acquired skills and knowledge like successful planning, problem solving, decision making, etc.

- **Contextual Performance:** these are actions that go beyond the description of the individual's tasks, those things proving that an employee goes above and beyond and can be manifested in social, organizational, and/or psychological areas. This performance can be associated with indicators such as resourcefulness, motivation, engagement, creativity, doing extra tasks, etc.
- **Adaptive Performance:** As its name suggests, this basically measures the ability of an individual to adapt to changes and circumstances, but also aspects like innovation and flexibility.
- **Counterproductive Work:** Like always, there are negative indicators that need to be measured such as tardiness, absenteeism, substance abuse, disregard of instructions, and safety regulations.

ii. Team Performance

Team performance is based on the strengths of working together as a group, and task proficiency is another important factor that contributes to high performance levels. Teams can be led by a single person or may consist of members from different departments. Some of these teams may be permanent, while others may only be active while they work on a specific project.

iii. Departmental Performance

This level of performance focuses on components that organizational units like departments own. When compared to individual or team performance, this level's performance frequently occurs at a slower cadence.

iv. Organization-Wide Performance

Organization-wide performance examines how strategies are put into action and is frequently owned at the executive level. It has been discovered that when organizations evaluate their strategic management and planning using internal and external assessments with a cascading system of goals, strategies, and plans, the effectiveness of achieving such goals is increased (Gardner and Matviak, 2022). It is significant to remember that dimensionality exists when evaluating organizational performance. You might be interested in learning how the organization is doing from the perspectives of regions; brands and products; departments and or processes (Gardner et al., 2022). Enhanced results are arguably the strongest justification for organizational performance management. Depending on the area that is being improved, these results can affect every aspect of a business. For example, a company seeking to increase employee productivity may notice higher output levels, greater engagement, higher skill levels, and so on.

What is leadership?

According to Igbaekemen and Odiviwri (2015), leadership is the ability to influence and guide those in an organization by making sound decisions, creating and articulating clear visions, and establishing achievable goals for followers. Researcher Folarin (2021) asserts that great leaders are able to do this consistently and effectively in a variety of circumstances, regardless of their power, popularity or colorful personality. A leader's success comes from their understanding of their followers and the relationship between individual goals and the overall group goal emphasized.

Leadership styles

Leadership gurus maintain there are several distinct styles of leadership, and some leaders tend to stick to one, while others prefer to blend modes in different scenarios or when interacting with varying people (Cooke, Klein and Wallis, 2013). Popularly known leadership styles include autocratic, bureaucratic, authoritative, coaching, coercive, charismatic, democratic, transactional, servant, situational and transformational (Vigoda-Gadot, 2012).

- **Leadership style and organizational performance**

Leadership styles have a significant impact on organizational performance. The leadership style influences the organizational culture, which in turn influences organizational performance. Klien et al.867rt (2013)

demonstrated this by employing the four-factor theory of leadership and data collected from 2,662 employees working in 311 organizations and concluded that the type of leadership style influences organizational culture and performance (Klein et al., 2013). The theoretical underpinnings of leadership styles and the influence of leadership on organizational performance are provided in this section.

- **Autocratic leadership and Organizational performance**

Autocratic leaders are typically known for their do as I say mentality. This type of leadership arises from a new position or assignment that involves people management, often with little to no prior experience (Chich-Jen, Mei-Ling and Wang, 2010). Unfortunately, this style of management can have serious consequences for the organization, as it stifles commitment, creativity and innovation through coercive practices. Furthermore, there is no shared vision among followers of autocratic leadership, who usually simply wait until the leader's inevitable failure and subsequent removal occurs (Chich-Jen et al. 2010).

- **Bureaucratic leadership and Organizational performance**

According to Germano (2010), bureaucratic leaders rely heavily on policy to reach organizational objectives. Policies are used to dictate execution, strategy, objectives and outcomes. Bureaucratic leaders find it easy to convince followers to adhere to policies. This sends a strong message that policy dictates direction. As a result of their focus on procedure and process, these leaders are often perceived as aloof and resistant to change. Studies by Vigoda-Gadot (2012) highlight the risks associated with this type of leadership often don't become apparent until it's too late. It is pointed out that the greatest benefit of leadership (motivating and developing people) is neglected when relying on policies and processes as motivation – this can demotivate employees and hinder desired results (Elenkov, 2002). In effect, both autocratic and bureaucratic leadership styles struggle to motivate and develop people, which can cause more damage than any short-term gains realized from such approaches.

- **Democratic or participative leadership and Organizational performance**

Research reveals that with democratic leadership also known as participative, the group is essentially self-governed, fostering an egalitarian spirit (Elenkov, 2002). However, there is an increased risk of poor decision-making and weak execution due to the immense effort needed to reach a consensus and the slow process of leading by fiat as supported by findings by Courtright, Oh and Wang (2011). One major issue with this type of approach is that it assumes everyone has an equal say and shared expertise when it comes to decisions, which is rarely true. Although democratic leadership sounds great in theory, it can often be overly cumbersome and laborious to achieve workable results (Zhu, 2002).

- **Charismatic leadership and Organizational performance**

Appraised by many researchers, it is pointed out that the charismatic leadership style is by far the most successful trait-driven style (Claudia, 2022). Another study by Folarin (2021) supports that leaders with charisma possess a vision and personality that motivate those around them to act on it. It is also indicated in a study by Giri and Santra (2010) that this style of leadership has typically been highly valued for its capacity to foster creativity and innovation, as well as its motivating factor. However, other studies criticize the style in that there are issues with charismatic leaders attributed to their tendency to leave for greener pastures. If they leave unexpectedly, the organization can be left directionless and without guidance, as they rarely develop replacements who have the same strength of personality (Claudia, 2022; Folarin, 2021). This often results in a lack of future leaders due to the elimination of competition by the charismatic leader's presence. Despite this downside, people are often encouraged by this type of leadership because it generally leaves them feeling satisfied and content (Bryman, 1992).

- **Situational leadership and Organizational performance**

Situational leadership theory proposes that the best leaders adjust continually by adjusting their leadership style for different situations or results (Boulter, 2010). Situational leaders employ their management style to meet the needs of the situation and team. This perspective presents a more advanced view of leading and can be an invaluable reference for experienced leaders who are very aware of organizational requirements and individual motivation. Most significantly, it gives experienced leaders the freedom to choose from numerous leadership variations (Cantrell, Fredendall and Laohavichien, 2009).

On the other hand, issues can arise when the wrong style is applied incompetently. Moreover, considering the dialog regarding some of the less efficient leadership styles such as autocratic and bureaucratic, this tactic necessitates a caution or warning concerning unintended or suboptimal outcomes when selecting one of these styles (Brown, 2009) supported. Having said that, situational leadership can serve as a handy framework for leaders to assess and utilize different styles for changing contexts with an aim towards refining leadership outcomes. Nonetheless, situational leadership is most effective when choosing more successful styles such as charismatic, transactional, and transformational (Cantrell et al., 2009; Coetzee and Mitonga-Monga, 2012).

- **Transactional leadership and Organizational performance**

Researchers Dixon and Hart (2010) posited that transactional leaders often referred to as “wheeler-dealers” of leadership styles are always willing to offer an incentive in exchange for following them. This could be anything from a good performance review to a promotion or change in duties. Findings from other studies highlight challenges with this style in that external incentives may not be sustainable, and this might create problems in the long run (Boulter, 2010). That being said, transactional leaders can display attributes of charismatic leaders, making them successful and beneficial for an organization - the only concern is sustainability.

- **Transformational leadership and Organizational performance**

Transformational leaders strive to create lasting change in those they lead (Adams and Adams, 2009). Rather than relying solely on their personality (charismatic) or manipulating followers (transactional), these leaders leverage knowledge, expertise, and vision to transform people in a manner that produces buy-in far beyond their own influence (Adams et al., 2009). Transformational leaders provide an invaluable service, as their goal is to empower others to grow and develop as contributors. In addition, this type of leadership is ideal for quickly changing environments that necessitate creative solutions and customer loyalty (Eisenbeiss, Knippenberg and Boerner, 2008).

- **Coaching Leadership aka Conscious Leadership and organizational performance**

A coaching leader focuses on identifying and nurturing the individual strengths of each member of the team and developing strategies that will enable teams to work better together (Amabile and Khaire, 2008). This style is similar to strategic and democratic leadership, but it emphasizes individual employees' success. A manager with this leadership style might help employees improve on their strengths by: Giving them new tasks to try, offering guidance, meeting to discuss constructive feedback (Ayman and Korabik, 2010; Amabile et al, 2008).

Methodology

This paper employed the Qualitative Content Analysis methodology. To generate themes, textual data ought to first go through content analysis, which is a thematic process as defined by Cresswell and Cresswell (2017). Secondary data for this study were gathered from academic papers, conference papers, and government publications from which findings and conclusions were drawn.

Findings and discussion

Findings from the evaluation suggest that the charismatic, transformational and participative leadership style are the most effective styles when contrasted with other styles in that they bring about higher morale and

productivity among employees, thereby improving overall organizational performance. Similarly, situational leadership also is effective when choosing more successful styles such as charismatic, transactional, and transformational approaches (Arnold and Feldman, 1986).

The findings of this study established that the goals of an organization in transactional leadership are the primary focus of transactional leaders, who also monitor progress toward those goals by evaluating team members' or employees' performance. For those who are unable to meet performance standards, these leaders frequently impose harsh penalties. Let's say Mr. Monyamane, a manager, examined the performance of his team and found that one staff-member didn't meet the standard. He informs the worker of the shortcoming and places her/him on a growth plan.

It is further established in this study that through motivation and encouragement, charismatic leaders have a positive effect on employee performance. They demand excellence and serve as role models for the actions required to achieve and enhance outcomes. A division manager named Basupi, for instance, motivates her team by setting a challenging sales target for them and giving the top salesperson a free ticket to Kasane (a tourism destination located in Botswana, Southern Africa).

It is pointed out here that, while servant leaders are compelled to serve from birth, before becoming managers or supervisors, these leaders frequently serve as volunteers in some capacity. Their foundation is to develop and empower their staff. They delegate authority and prioritize their employees' needs. Imagine that your boss works every holiday so that you and your colleagues can spend time with our families.

Furthermore, it is revealed that democratic or participatory leaders have a close relationship with their workforce. They consult to clarify the specifications of a task, assignment, or project before letting the staff choose the best course of action. These executives think that involving workers in the majority of decisions will boost output and teamwork. For instance, imagine that a large conglomerate has acquired a small business, and the acquisition director requests that her team come up with and discuss the best transition strategy to merge the two businesses. This approach provides for participative and inclusive decision making.

These findings also suggest that transactional leaders and authoritarian leaders share many characteristics, in that they both demand excellence and impose harsh penalties for anything less. They exert control over others and believe that workers should obey their orders because they are the subject matter experts. Consider Mr. Bogosi, a new manager of a training consultancy, assigning each trainer their respective roles, responsibilities, and performance time limits. He also talks about the severe consequences for not meeting the training expectations. This strategy is probably going to make the trainers angry and at the same time afraid.

Masterful at adjusting to the needs of their workforce are situational leaders. This study discovered that situational leaders are acquainted with the traits of various leadership philosophies. They select a leadership style that fosters influence and support while boosting output after analysing their workforce. It is suggested here that it's important to modify and adapt the style as the organization grows so that the goals can be met at the appropriate time.

Leaders in coaching actively encourage independent problem-solving and skill development. They contribute to a company's long-term vision as valuable mentors, frequently even after leaving a company, and help it achieve ambitious business goals by developing a strong company culture. Due to their sense of community on the team, this leadership style can inspire workers. The ability to create diverse and exciting teams where each member contributes something unique acknowledges that each employee is unique. This leader places a strong emphasis on high performance, with workers who can communicate effectively and value specialized skill sets in order to complete tasks.

At last, it is revealed in this study, that bureaucratic leaders share traits with transactional leaders since they put the needs and objectives of the organization first. In this environment, roles and policies are clearly defined, and rules and guidelines are strictly followed, according to the defined hierarchical structure. Employees who violate this structure are subject to repercussions for their non-compliance. Outside of their domain, these leaders are not particularly adaptable. For instance, Mr. T., who previously worked in the private sector in a more democratic setting where his opinion counted, is now employed by the government, where protocol is followed in making decisions.

Summary and conclusion

This paper examined leadership styles and concluded that the charismatic leadership produces favorable outcomes for employees, which in turn improves organizational performance when compared with other leadership approaches. Nonetheless, situational leadership is most effective when choosing more successful styles such as charismatic, transactional, and transformational.

In this study is established that leadership is the art of influencing others and that leaders are visionaries who motivate, persuade, inspire, guide, and direct the other members to do the task assigned for the attainment of specific goals. Charisma, consideration for others, knowledge updating, constructive guidance, dependability, integrity, respect for others, etc. are the underlying qualities that a leader must possess. Good leaders can bring transformation in the lives of people. They can even bring revolutionary social changes.

Effective leaders should be stern but at the same time flexible. They should be trustworthy and honest, and hold strong ethical values and standards. Effective communication involving both speaking and listening skills is key to good leadership. Insight and foresight are the two other qualities. Visualizing the company's progress and capturing the current and upcoming trends can do a great deal. Risk-taking is another quality of an effective leader. The leaders must have the wisdom to understand when to take low, moderate, and high risks depending upon the situation in demand.

It is established here that autocratic leaders form decisions and make choices without looking for suggestions from any other members. They don't have consent to check with the leader before execution, which can create chaos and calls for the mistake. If the execution does not meet the expectation, then it's not well taken by the leader. This leadership proved not to be very effective, as there was no cohesiveness between the members and the leader. A low sense of belongingness, commitment, etc. can be expected with this kind of leadership. One of the few areas during crisis management in which quick and stern decisions are to be taken.

On the other hand, bureaucratic leaders are characteristically found in established institutions or extremely controlled surroundings where abiding by strict rules is significant. Innovative notions can be excluded, as the organization is effective with the present procedures in place. Applying somewhat novel and diverse ideas might take away the resources if it's not practicable. This leadership style smothers innovative ideas among staff and such organizations will be resistant to change.

Transformational leaders are engrossed in constant enhancement. They continually drive the team from their comfort zone. Transactional leadership is more or less related to charismatic leadership, which influences others through charisma. The leaders can be very communicative, emotional, and expressive enough to bring a transformation. Constructive leaders possess optimism and they spread strength and positivity among the team members (Den, Greenbaum, Folger and Piccolo, 2010). Effective leaders can turn challenging situations into opportunities because they are concerned and considerate of the well-being of the team members. They work as a part of the team without discriminating themselves from others. Good leaders are goal- and result-oriented and try to maximize successful results in efficient and effective ways.

Implications

These findings are especially relevant to prospective and current leaders; thus, it is crucial to understand your leadership style and its impact on the performance of the organization. It's always important to ask for feedback to understand how you're doing. As a result, when you gather feedback from your junior you'll be able to choose the best leadership style on the spot and apply its traits to your regular management responsibilities. Understanding your leadership philosophies could help you get better with little feedback. You can proactively address areas that need improvement because every leadership style has its flaws. This is important because some workers might be reluctant to participate in an anonymous survey.

According to the study by Choi (2007) titled “The lessons of exemplary models for democratic governance “, it is apparent that good instincts are a necessity for leaders, and many people concentrate on their own habits and experiences as they establish their leadership style. You might want to begin taking notes as you begin your journey toward leadership. You can become a confident and capable leader by outlining your approach to various situations or issues. However, you might want to change your strategy if you notice that some interactions aren't going as you had hoped. Trying out a leadership style is one more way to determine if it is appropriate for you. Make an outline of each leadership style that interests you. After that, go over your notes before your following meeting to see how you can apply this communication style to your interactions.

Leaders can use leadership assessment tools to evaluate their teams and themselves as well. It can be simpler to comprehend your strengths and abilities if you take leadership assessment. It can bring to the surface traits and behaviours you might not be aware of and can provide you with a clear path for development. According to their industry and the challenges they face, leaders may use a combination of the aforementioned leadership philosophies. You can become a more powerful leader by deciding on a leadership style that works for you. Your management style has a big impact on how your direct reports perceive you, regardless of how big or small your team is. It determines how well your team collaborates to accomplish the objectives of your business.

Recommendations

The recommendations presented here are meant to form part of how aspiring leaders and current leaders may improve their leadership style in order to enhance organizational performance.

- **Get to know yourself**

Each leader follows a different path to self-discovery, others place a higher priority on creative writing, others outline their strengths and weaknesses and identify opportunities for growth, while others take risks and try new things towards self-actualization. Other methods to discover more about yourself include social interactions and or social networking. Finding out who you truly are is one key crucial step towards building leadership skills.

- **Define your leadership values**

Understanding what's important to you and where you struggle is much easier if you know your values; having your values mapped out can be very helpful because being a leader requires working according to standards and making ethical decisions. Thus, one should scrutinize defining moments in their career life and outline their values based on how they interact with people, how they made decisions, trends in their achievements and challenges they faced. Then, search for themes, put related items together for analysis and interpretation; this output may help one understand their reactions, strengths and weaknesses, and thus be able to lay a solid foundation for one's core values.

- **Consider employing charismatic leadership**

The charismatic leadership style brings forth advantageous outcomes for both subordinates and leaders, which in turn improves organizational performance when related to other leadership approaches. This can be done in connection with other styles such as situational and transformational.

- **Accommodate feedback from subordinates**

To better understand how you're leading your team, it's always important to get feedback from them, so you are able to select the best leadership style better suited to the organization. So, it is imperative that one pays close attention to the feedback they receive from colleagues and subordinates. Through this, one may identify areas for improvement and the best leaderships style suited to their team and organization.

- **Take stock of your leadership journey**

As you start down the path to leadership, you might want to document your journey. By describing your strategy for dealing with various situations or problems, you can develop into a self-assured and competent leader. Leaders must have strong instincts built upon their character and career experiences fostered to maximize organizational performance.

- **Utilize leadership assessment tools to determine strengths and weaknesses**

Leaders can evaluate themselves and their teams using leadership assessment tools. Taking leadership assessments can make it easier to understand your strengths, weaknesses and talents. It can reveal characteristics and behaviors that you might not be aware of and show you a clear path for growth which may include further training on leadership skills.

List of References

- i. Adams, B., & Adams, C. (2009). Transformation, *Leadership Excellence*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 14-15.
- ii. Adebakin, O. I., & Gbadamusi, E. A. (1996). The practices of organizational leadership. Ibadan. Adeogun printing press.
- iii. Amabile, T. M., & Khaire, M. (2008). Creativity and the role of the leader, *Harvard business review*, vol. 86, no. 10, pp. 100.
- iv. Amos, T., Ristow, A., & Staude, G. (1999). Transformational Leadership and Organizational Effectiveness in the Administration of Cricket in South Africa. *South African Journal of Business Management*, 30, a749.
- v. Arnold, H. J., & Feldman, D. C. (1986). Organisational behaviour, new behaviour. New York: McGraw Hill Book Company.
- vi. Ayman, R., & Korabik, K. (2010). Leadership, *American Psychologist*, vol. 65, no. 3, pp. 157-170.
- vii. Bass, B., & Avolio, B. J. (1994). Improving Organizational Effectiveness Through Transformational Leadership. London: SAGE Publications.
- viii. Bhargavi, S., & Yaseen, A. (2016). Leadership Styles and Organizational Performance. *Strategic Management Quarterly*, 4(1), pp. 87-117.
- ix. Boyatzis R., Goleman. D., & McKee, A. (2002). Primal leadership: Realizing the power of emotional intelligence. Harvard Business School Press.
- x. Boulter, J. (2010). Recovery Leadership. *Leadership Excellence*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 13-13.
- xi. Brown, T. (2009). Leadership in challenging times. *Business Strategy Review*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 36.
- xii. Bryman, A. (1992). Charisma and Leadership in Organizations. Sage, London.
- xiii. Cantrell, R. S., Fredendall, L. D., & Laohavichien, T. (2009). The effects of transformational and transactional leadership on quality improvement. *Quality Management Journal*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 7-24.
- xiv. Chich-Jen, S., Mei-Ling, T., & Wang, F. J. (2010). Effect of leadership style on organizational performance as viewed from human resource management strategy. *African Journal of Business Management*, 4(18), pp. 3924-3936.
- xv. Choi, S. (2007). The lessons of exemplary models for democratic governance. *International Journal of Leadership Studies*, 2(3), pp. 243-262.
- xvi. Claudia, F. (2022). Comparing Different Leadership Styles. <https://study.com/academy/lesson/comparing-different-leadership-styles.html>

- xvii. Coetzee, M., & Mitonga-Monga, J. (2012). Perceived leadership style and employee participation. *African Journal of Business Management*, 6(15).
- xviii. Courtright, S. H., Oh, I.S., & Wang, G. (2011). Transformational leadership and performance across criteria and levels: A meta-analytic review of 25 years of research. *Group & Organization Management*, 36(2), pp. 223-270.
- xix. Cooke, R. A., Klein, A. S., & Wallis, J. (2013). The impact of leadership styles on organizational culture and firm effectiveness: An empirical study. *Journal of Management & Organization*, 19(3), pp. 241-254.
- xx. Creswell, J.W., & Creswell, J.D. (2017). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. 4th Edition, Sage, Newbury Park.
- xxi. Den H, D. N., Greembaum, R., Folger, R., & Piccolo, R. F. (2010). The Relationship between Ethical Leadership and Core Job Characteristics. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 31, 259-278. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.627>
- xxii. Dixon, M. L., & Hart, L. K. (2010). The impact of path-goal leadership styles on work group effectiveness and turnover intention. *Journal of Managerial Issues*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 52-69.
- xxiii. Eisenbeiss, S., van Knippenberg, D., & Boerner, S. (2008). Transformational leadership and team innovation: Integrating team climate principles. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, vol. 93, no. 6, pp. 1438.
- xxiv. Ejiofor, P. (1989). *Foundation of business administration*. Onitsha Africa Feb. Publishing Limited. Leadership on organisational performance in Nigeria.374. Published with open access at journalbinet.com EISSN:2412-8279, © 2019 The Authors, Review paper.
- xxv. Elenkov, D. S. (2002). Effects of leadership on organizational performance in Russian companies. *Journal of Business Research*, 55(6), pp. 467-480.
- xxvi. Folarin, K. (2021). Leadership Styles, Organizational Performance and Effectiveness among Sub-Saharan African Employees. *American Journal of Leadership and Governance*, 6(1), 24 - 36. <https://doi.org/10.47672/ajlg.743>
- xxvii. Folan P., Browne, J., & Jagdev, H. (2007). Performance: It's Meaning and Content for Today's Business Research, *Computers in Industry*, vol. 58, no. 7
- xxviii. Giri, V. N., & Santra, T. (2010). Effects of job experience, career stage, and hierarchy on leadership style. *Singapore Management Review*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 85-93.
- xxix. Gavrea, C., Ilies, L., & Stegorean, R. (2011). Determinants of organizational performance: The case of Romania. *Management & Marketing*, 6(2), pp. 285-300
- xxx. Germano, M. A. (2010). Leadership Style and Organizational Impact. <http://alaapa.org/newsletter/2010/06/08/spotlight/>
- xxxi. Gardner, K. H., & Matviak, I. (2022). Performance Management Shouldn't Kill Collaboration. <https://hbr.org/2022/09/performance-management-shouldnt-kill-collaboration>
- xxxii. Igbaekemen, G. O., & Odivwri, J. E. (2015). Impact of leadership style on organization performance: A critical literature review. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 5(5), pp. 1-7.
- xxxiii. Iqbal, N., Anwar, S., & Haider, N. (2015). Effect of leadership style on employee performance. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*, 5(5), pp. 1-6
- xxxiv. Judge, T. A., & Piccolo, R. F. (2004). Transformational and Transactional Leadership: A Meta-Analytic Test of Their Relative Validity. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 89(5), 755–768. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.89.5.755>
- xxxv. Lebas, M. J. (1995). Performance Measurement and Performance Management, *International Journal of Production*, vol. 41, no. 1-3
- xxxvi. Messick, D. M., & Kramer, R. M. (2004). *The psychology of leadership, New Perspectives and Research*. London: Longman Publishing Co.
- xxxvii. Muijs, D. (2011). *Leadership and motivation*, New York: Random House. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/303758160_Leadership_and_Motivation
- xxxviii. Mullins, L. J. (2002). *Management and organizational behaviour*, (5 th Edition) Britain: Pearson Educational Ltd.

- xxxix. Rachin. (2001). Impact of leadership on organization. New Jersey: Prentice Hall Inc.
- xl. Stogdill, R. M. (1948). Personal Factors Associated with Leadership: A Survey of the Literature. Reprinted in Bass, B(Eds), Bass, B.M., Stogdill (1990), Handbook of Leadership: Theory. Research and Managerial Applications (3rd Ed), New York: Free Press. J. Psychol., 25: 35-71
- xli. Suri, S. (2016). Influence of Leadership Style on Employee Motivation and Performance. International Journal of Research in Management, 5, 65-71.
- xlii. Tandoh, V. (2011). Effect of Leadership Behaviours on Employee Performance in Guinness Ghana Breweries Limited. Ashanti: Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology. <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajbm.v30i1.749>
- xliii. Vigoda-Gadot, E. (2012). Leadership style, organizational politics, and employees' performance: An empirical examination of two competing models. American Journal of Business and Management, 36(5), pp. 661- 683.
- xliv. Wholey, J. S. (1996). Formative and Summative Evaluation: Related Issues in Performance Measurement, American Journal of Evaluation, vol. 17, no. 2.
- xlvi. Qiu, J.H. (2008). The Executive Leadership and Performance Management. Taipei: Showwe.
- xlvi. Zhu, X. W. (2002). The impacts of leadership, member satisfaction, and teamwork quality on team performance: An example on ERP project team, Taoyuan, Taiwan: National Central University.